

LEADCOR

LEADERSHIP DEVELOPMENT FOR OCCUPATIONAL
STRESS REDUCTION IN CORRECTIONAL SETTINGS

LEADCOR User's Manual

Leadership Competencies in Correctional Settings

Module I - Stress and Burnout

www.leadership-corrections.org

This page was intentionally left blank

LEADCOR - Leadership development for occupational stress reduction in correctional setting

LEADCOR User's Manual

Leadership Competencies in Correctional Settings

Project's website - <https://www.leadership-corrections.org/>

For more information on this user's manual or about the project, please contact:

ips@prisonsystems.eu

Authors

Ana Rita Pires, IPS_Innovative Prison Systems

Ângela Fernandes, IPS_Innovative Prison Systems

Peer-Review

Ana Margarida Nascimento, IPS_Innovative Prison Systems

Carolina Pereira, IPS_Innovative Prison Systems

Pedro das Neves, IPS_Innovative Prison Systems

Multimedia and Design

Sílvia Silva, IPS_Innovative Prison Systems

Collaborators/Translations

Adrian Neagoe - Sindicatul National al Politistilor de Penitenciare

Isabelle Storme - Le Service Public Federal Justice

Kathleen Van De Vijver - Le Service Public Federal Justice

Mihaela Pinteaa-Traian - Penitenciarul Baia Mare

Rhianon Williams - Bremen Senate of Justice and Constitution

Vítor Costa - BSafeLab/Universidade da Beira Interior (UBI)

This document was produced within the scope of the *Leadership development for occupational stress reduction in correctional setting (LEADCOR) Project, 2019-1-PT01-KA204-061285*.

This publication reflects the views only of the author, and the Portuguese Agency Erasmus + and European Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Table of Content

Module I - Stress and Burnout	5
Chapter 1 - Understanding Stress	7
Sub-chapter 1.1 - The importance of well-being and mental health in workplace settings.....	7
Sub-chapter 1.2 - What is stress?	15
Sub-chapter 1.3 - Transactional Model of Stress.....	21
Sub-chapter 1.4 - Levels of Stressors.....	26
What did I learn?	32
Chapter 2 - Stress at Workplace	33
Sub-chapter 2.1 - Work and Stress.....	33
Sub-chapter 2.2 - The interaction between the task, the individual, and the employer	40
Sub-chapter 2.3 - Work and Burnout.....	45
What did I learn?.....	50
Chapter 3 - Stress and Leadership	51
Sub-chapter 3.1 - The importance of Leadership in stress management at the workplace	51
What did I learn?	53
References	53

Module I - Stress and Burnout

Overview of the Module I

Welcome to the **Module I** about **Stress and Burnout!** This Module is divided in **3 Chapters:**

Understanding Stress

Stress at Workplace

Stress and Leadership

- **In the Chapter “Understanding Stress”, we will focus on the subchapters:**
 - The importance of well-being and mental health in workplace settings;
 - What is Stress;
 - Transactional Model of Stress;
 - What are the levels of stressors.

- **In the Chapter “Stress at Workplace”, we will focus on the subchapters:**
 - Work and Stress;
 - The Interaction Between the Task, the Individual, and the Employer;
 - Work and Burnout.

- **In the Chapter “Stress and Leadership”, we will focus on the subchapter:**
 - The Importance of Leadership in Stress Management at Workplace.

By the end of this module, you will be able to:

- ◆ Understand the concept of stress
- ◆ Understand how to cope with and prevent stress
- ◆ Identify sources of stress and understand individual differences
- ◆ Comprehend the relation between work and stress
- ◆ Identify the effects of work stress
- ◆ Recognise the working conditions that cause stress
- ◆ Comprehend the relation between work and burnout
- ◆ Understand the importance of Leadership in stress management at the Workplace

Chapter 1 - Understanding Stress

Sub-chapter 1.1 - The importance of well-being and mental health in workplace settings

The scientific literature on **prison staff stress** and **stress management** asserts that prisons are stressful working places with complex challenges for staff, namely the balance between control/safety and care/rehabilitation while dealing with the potential to be harmed.¹ Therefore, **occupational stress** (which corresponds to psychological stress related to one's job; the work-related stress) has gathered the attention of both researchers and practitioners. This attention resulted in the proliferation of scientific papers in the field of job stress and intervention programmes that address stress management and aim at reducing its negative impact.

Focusing on stress in organisational contexts, several definitions can be found in the literature for work/job/occupational stress, namely:

- The National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) defines stress as *“the harmful physical and emotional responses that occur when the requirements of the job do not match the capabilities, resources, or needs of the worker.”*;
- *“Job stress comes from the nature of the task itself (for example, complexity, difficulty level) and the conditions the individual is operating under (for example, time pressure, working conditions)”*²; another author defines it.

Multiple **sources of job stress** have been identified and organised in different groups, such as:^{3, 4, 5}

- **Physical environment** – includes, among others, working conditions and factors such as temperature, noise, toxicity, vibration, lighting, hygiene, ergonomics.

- **Individual** – such as the absence of career plans, work overload, role conflict and ambiguity, interpersonal relations related to the tasks.
- **Group/relational/psychosocial** - such as lack of group cohesion, inadequate group climate, lack of communication, lack of social support.
- **Organisational** – organisational structure, climate, job design (autonomy, feedback, monotony, repetition), new technologies.
- **Extra-organisational** – work-family conflict, family crisis, parental/marital roles, grieving, stressors from other activities (legal problems, substance use, financial problems, etc.).

Additional sources of job stress can also be considered, such as the ones related to time, that is, shift work, changes in time zone, and urgent tasks or tasks with very short deadlines.⁴

The **prison context** presents **several stressors** that put those working in this environment at a **higher risk of experiencing stress**. Two decades have already passed since it was identified⁶ ten psychosocial risk factors related to stress reactions in correctional officers' literature:

Figure 1. Psychosocial risk factors related to stress reactions in correctional officers

Several studies focused on finding the **consequences of occupational stress** within the **correctional environment** were conducted, and the results were clear.

The negative work attitudes (turnover intention), specific role problems (perceived dangerousness of the job), and a professional punitive orientation predicted **higher levels of job stress**. In turn, positive work attitudes (participation in decision-making, being satisfied with the job, and being committed) and a human-oriented professional orientation were predictors of **low levels of job stress**.⁷

Stressors related to organisational structure and climate were the ones who predicted correctional officers' job stress more consistently. Therefore, "unclear goals and policies, lack of decision-making ability, lack of support from the organisation and lack of organisational justice" appears to be related to higher levels of job stress.⁸

Some **instruments** provide valuable information regarding measuring work stress, life stress, and psychological distress. These instruments consider the explored risk, protective factors and coping strategies.⁹ Themes usually explored in staff stress studies such as "work satisfaction, social support, psychosocial risks, organisational commitment, psychological well-being, and violence" were recognised.

Also, **risk/protective factors** like "overwork, lack of material and human resources, degree of contact and perceptions about the prisoners, overcrowding, perceptions of fear

or danger, the paradox of punishment/re-education, and the stress of shift changes” were identified.

Some authors¹⁰ found that female correctional officers tend to report higher levels of job stress than male officers. They also found that stress is higher in correctional officers with more years of experience on the job and that support from both supervisors and peers decreases levels of job stress.

Three hundred and thirteen prison wardens in the U.S. were studied.¹¹ It was found that both **conflicting job expectations and unmanageable workload were positively related to work-related stress levels**. Job autonomy was negatively associated with work-related stress. The institution's size was positively related to the work-related stress levels of prison wardens, meaning that a bigger institution, higher work-related stress levels.

In their analysis of **1802 prison officers** from 45 prisons across Ohio and Kentucky¹², examined the applicability of the job demand-control (-support) model of stress and found that **experiencing victimisation and greater job demands were related to higher levels of perceived stress**, while perceived control over inmates and support from co-workers and supervisors, were associated with less stress. Facility violence was linked to higher levels of officer stress across prisons. Exploring the demand-control model of job stress with a sample of 171 prison staff workers in Iran, it was found¹³ that higher levels of job stress were reported by lieutenants, followed by security officers and rehabilitation professionals.

Job demands such as **emotional demands appear to be related to burnout of correctional officers**¹⁴, which, in turn, is positively associated with negative outcomes such as **drinking behaviours**. Correctional officers' alcohol consumption was also studied, and negative correlations were found with **burnout dimensions** (professional efficacy, emotional exhaustion, and cynicism) and **psychological disturbance**. It was also found between emotional **exhaustion/cynicism** and **frequency of physical exercise**, meaning that the higher the burnout levels, the lower the frequency of physical exercise.¹⁵

Exploring the **job demands-resources model of work stress** with a representative sample of prison officers in South Korea, it was found¹⁶ that while job demands directly influence burnout, **job resources** (lack of resources such as social support) **have an indirect relationship with burnout through basic psychological needs**. This means that the lack of resources hinders the satisfaction of basic psychological needs (such as autonomy and competence), leading to **burnout of prison officers**. The workload, intensity, and working hours (job demands) had powerful negative effects on **mental health status** (worsening officers mental health).¹⁷

On the resources side, **positive working relationships** and **role clarity** appear as protective factors for **prison officers' mental health**. Job resources such as **input into decision-making** and the **quality of supervision** had a (negative) significant impact on job stress, meaning that **job stress will decrease in the presence of perceived quality supervision and involvement in decision-making**. On the other hand, job demands - namely work overload and fear of victimisation - were also significant predictors of job stress.¹⁸

Job resources have an indirect relationship with **burnout through basic psychological needs**

Mental health status

Role clarity, instrumental communication, and training views (all considered job resources) showed no significant relation with job stress.¹⁸ With a sample of **501 correctional officers** working in Texas¹⁹, it was found that job demands, namely the **fear of workplace victimisation, role strain, and boundary violations** (the perception that a professional relationship with a client is being violated), were a significant predictor of **work stress**. On the other hand, studied job resources, namely if staff sees inmates as manageable and supervisory support had a significant negative impact on job stress. However, some job resources also contributed to increased job stress, namely **prison rules** (obeying organisational policies and regulations) and **viewing inmates as amiable**.

Nigeria has explored the demands-resources model with a sample of **120 Nigerian prison staff**.²⁰ Perceived **dangers of the job**, followed by **role overload**, were significant predictors of **job stress**. On the other resources side, support from supervision was related to low levels of perceived job stress. Nevertheless, instrumental communication and job variety showed no significant relationship with job stress.

Role ambiguity was associated with **stress**, meaning that the higher the ambiguity, the higher the reported stress levels. However, this relation was only significant for female jail officers.²¹ On the other hand, role conflict appears to increase job stress but only for male jail staff.²¹

Despite a general theoretical and empirical relation between higher job resources and low job stress, job resources such as job autonomy showed no relation with job stress.^{20, 22}

Considering the prison officer role, **negative job characteristics** such as **job dangerousness**, described as “the risk and harm associated with one’s immediate **work environment**”^{23 (p.39)}, can also represent a **potential stressor**. In fact, a study with 225 prison officers from a province in China found that **job dangerousness was the only consistent antecedent of job stress**. Similarly, a greater threat of harm was associated with higher stress levels in both probation/parole officers and residential officers.²⁴

The dangerousness of the function was also a relevant determinant of **job stress**²⁵, contributing to both male and female officers' levels of job stress.

Input into **decision-making** has also been studied related to **staff stress**. Results from a study with staff from community-based corrections showed that **less input into decision-making** was associated with **higher levels of stress** than their counterparts.²⁴ A comparable result was found in a study exploring gendered effects in job stress. However, input into decision making was only significantly related to job stress (more input – less job stress) in female jail staff.²¹

Supervisor support appears to be a **protective factor for prison officers**, significantly **decreasing reported values of job stress**^{26, 19} of both male and female officers.^{25, 21}

Increasing job resources such as **supportive mentoring** and **effective socialisation** also seems to **protect against burnout** in a sample of 117 correctional officer newcomers with a formal mentor at the institution.²⁷ However, research is not unanimous on this topic.

Adequate **educational training** can also be a protective factor for staff stress levels, considering that less adequate training was a predictor of community correctional staff's higher stress levels.²⁴ In fact, opportunities for professional development are recognised as a valuable job resource.²⁸

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

A large, empty rectangular box with a thin black border, intended for taking notes or observations.

Sub-chapter 1.2 - What is stress?

In this sub-chapter we will focus on what is stress. **Stress** can be defined as “physiological and/or psychological arousal that occurs when individuals perceive a threat to something of value to them and that threat taxes or exhausts the resources, they have available to confront it”.^{1 (p. 179)}

Stress is a physiological experience that can be felt at a very individual level. One person can handle the extreme pressure and anxiety over a task that is coming up, but another might look at the same task and see it as an exciting challenge. The symptoms and conditions that originate stress are individual. Usually, when feeling stress, the body reacts with a **wave of hormones and chemicals that can lead to a fight-or-flight response.** This means that the person's reaction may be to fight or run away from the stressor.²

Depending on the circumstances, **stress is not necessarily bad**, even though it is usually discussed in a negative context. There is an opportunity when someone experiences stress because it offers potential gain. It increases focus and attention, productivity and performance, helps to adapt to an uncomfortable situation, activates the memory, etc. Despite the idea that stress represents a negative experience, with adverse consequences for both physical, psychological, and social health, research has shown that **a certain level of stress can be beneficial to face environmental demands appropriately.** This is important when we think about work stress, considering that

employees will be facing certain levels of stress (related to the job demands) that do not necessarily leave them in exhaustion and can be beneficial for optimal performance. However, when employees lack resources to face job demands, “bad” stress (distress) happens as well as its consequences.³

Stress can also be negative when it is related to **constraints** and **demands**. **Constraints** prevent people from doing what they desire. **Demands** represent the loss of something desired. These are the two conditions needed for potential stress to become real stress (if there is uncertainty over the outcome, and the outcome must be important).³

Stress is highest for those who do not know if they will win or lose and lowest for those who feel that winning (or losing) is inevitable. Even so, people can recognise winning (or losing) as an inevitability, but if it is important, they are still likely to experience a level of stress.

The **General Adaptation Syndrome (GAS)**⁴ describes the three phases’ people experience when they encounter stressors, respond, and try to adapt:

Figure 2. Phases’ people experience when they encounter stressors, respond, and try to adapt
Source: Adapted from Healthline

- **Alarm** - physical reaction a person experiences upon a stressor. The reaction could include, for example, tense muscles, dilated pupils, an elevation of blood pressure.
- **Resistance** - if the stressor persists, the person prepares himself/herself physiologically and psychologically to fight and resist it. Initially, the person will respond to the stressor with plenty of energy, however, if the stressor persists, he/she will eventually feel fatigued, and resistance will wear down.
- **Exhaustion** - continuous, unsuccessful resistance eventually leads to the collapse of physical and mental defenses. This phase is the result of persistent or chronic stress. Struggling with stress for long periods can drain the physical, emotional, and mental resources to the point where the body no longer has the strength to fight stress.

There are some signs that can indicate the level of exhaustion a person can feel. **These signs of exhaustion can include:**⁴

Figure 3. Signs of exhaustion

The level of exhaustion a person can feel can be influenced by different stressors. There are **several categories of stressors**, namely:

Figure 4. Categories of stressors

Let us try to understand the characteristics that a situation must have to be taken as a stressor.

The psychologist Richard Lazarus mentions that a stress-inducing situation is anyone in which the relationship between the **individual and the environment is evaluated as exceeding their resources**, thus harming their well-being. We can refer, in other words, that a person is in **stress** when they feel that the degree of **demand** that a given circumstance creates is **greater than their response capacity**, that is, the means they have (personal or social) to overcome it with success.⁵

If we consider the **requirements** posed by the situation and the **individual's skills and resources (personal or social)**, we can deduce three possible hypotheses in the balance **between them**.

- When an individual **has enough skills and resources** to create adequate responses to the demands, life occurs within the controlled patterns of stress;
- When **the demands are greater than the individual's ability to respond**, he/she lives in a situation of exhausting stress;

- When the **skills and resources are superior to the requirements**, the degree of stress is minimal. However, in the latter case, if the conditions are too low, the boredom they give rise to can be a stress factor.

- 1** Enough skills and resources
- 2** The **demands are greater than the individual's ability to respond**
- 3** When the **skills and resources are superior to the requirements**

The same stress condition causes people to react differently. **A stress-inducing circumstance for one person is not necessarily so for another.** The importance of circumstances is seen in numerous cases. We can already refer that what determines the variability of these reactions is the appraisal that each person makes of the circumstances of the environment in which they find themselves. It depends on the way the person was brought up, on the life experiences they have gone through on learning about how to deal with unpleasant circumstances, on the (psychological) values and beliefs developed, in short, on the **personal** and **social skills** and **resources** they have. It should be noted that stress-inducing circumstances do not only arise from individual to individual. In the same human being, what is likely to be stressed at some point in life may not be at a different stage.⁶

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

A large, empty rectangular box with a thin black border, intended for taking notes or observations.

Sub-chapter 1.3 - Transactional Model of Stress

In this sub-chapter we will focus on the Transactional Model of Stress. The term **appraisal** corresponds to **an individual's evaluation and interpretation of the stressor and their ability to cope with it.**¹ When an imbalance happens between a person's appraisal and the demands of the situation and their estimation of their ability to meet those demands, **they will experience a stress response.**

Appraisal is not necessarily a conscious process; it is **subjective** and **highly personal** and **depends on our perception of the ability to cope** with it. For example, in the **prison context**, a stressful situation may correspond to a sudden change of schedule and shift for a correctional officer. However, to his/her colleague, this may be an ordinary situation that does not translate to feeling stress.

There are **two different types of appraisals**: primary and secondary.² The **primary appraisal** happens when we evaluate or “judge” the significance of the situation. Outcomes of the primary appraisal may be judging that the situation is irrelevant, benign-positive, or stressful. If we perceive the situation as stressful, we then engage in additional appraisal:²

- **Harm/loss**: assessment of what is lost already;
- **Threat**: assessment of harm/loss that has not occurred yet, but might;
- **Challenge**: assessment of potential growth from the situation.

On the other hand, we have the **secondary appraisal** when evaluating our **coping** options, resources, and options for dealing with a stressful situation. Coping options and

resources may be internal (for example, strength and determination) or external (for example, money, support from family or peers).²

Lastly, the **reappraisal** occurs when reconsidering which additional resources we need to cope with the situation; this means reappraising the situation while considering the available coping resources and reappraising the coping resources while considering the reappraised threat.²

Figure 5. Types of appraisals and coping
Source: Adapted from Wikimedia Commons

When we cannot escape a stress response, we need to cope with it effectively. **Coping** is the process of constantly changing cognitive and behavioural efforts to manage specific internal and/or external stressors appraised as exceeding a person's resources. There are several different approaches to coping with stress, namely:

- **Emotion-focused coping** focuses on the emotional and physiological effects of stress (the goal is to feel better during stress);³
- **Problem-focused coping** focuses on altering the causes of stress (the goal is to modify or remove the stressor itself);³
- **Prevention of stress** by altering the physical environment or building resistance.

Emotion-focused coping is a way of dealing with a stressful situation by **activating cognitive or behavioural responses to emotions resulting from stress**. This type of coping is rarely ideal when used exclusively, especially in prison. One aspect can hinder this type of coping, and that is **avoidance**. Avoidance is problematic, especially when it prevents effective behavioural reactions.³

When people use effective emotion-focused coping, they will **engage in positive emotions** (for example, finding the positive during the negative, counting blessings). They will also **find benefits or meaning**, looking for silver linings. The people using this type of coping will also **engage in an emotional approach**, taking time to express emotions and process thinking. This type of coping gives the person time to

- Exercise
- Take a bath
- Give yourself a pep talk
- Meditate

Activating **cognitive or behavioural responses to emotions** resulting from stress

Avoidance is problematic, especially when it prevents effective behavioural reactions

Engage in **positive emotions**

Engage in an **emotional approach**

accommodate the stressor, accept the reality and incorporate it into lifestyle or even life.

Problem-focused coping seeks to tackle the stressor head-on. Examples include asking for assistance, soliciting expert help, seeking out information (education), using logic and reason to avoid exaggerating the stressor, engaging in problem-solving to a plan of action, acting on steps to be taken.³

- Work on managing time
- Ask for support
- Establish healthy boundaries
- Create a to-do list

Tackle the stressor head-on

Asking for assistance, soliciting expert help, seeking out information, using logic and reason, engaging in problem-solving to act

Several tips may help to **prevent stress**:

- Build social support, connect with individuals or groups;
- Exercise and develop a healthy lifestyle;
- Utilise adequate time and financial management;
- Find environments with less stress (noise, crowding, violence/safety);
- Prepare for anticipated stressors (changing shifts, lack of staff, assignment of tasks or new tasks).

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

A large, empty rectangular box with a thin black border, intended for taking notes or observations.

Sub-chapter 1.4 - Levels of Stressors

There are several differences among people and stressors that cause them a reaction. Specific stress may be a great challenge for a person, but it may pose no threat to others. We will attempt to answer this by looking at the **three sources of stress** — **individual**, **organisational**, and **environmental** — and then add the concept of human perception to understand this riddle.^{1, 2, 3}

Figure 6. Sources of stress
Source: Adapted from Lumen Learning

The first of the three sources of stress is the **individual**. People might experience stressful events at work, for example, one time per week or during a couple of weeks. However, those kinds of temporary, individual stresses are not what we are looking at here. We are looking for deeper, longer-term stress.

- **Family stress** - for example, marriages ending, issues with children, an ailing parent are stressful situations that an employee cannot leave at home when he/she comes to work;
- **Financial stress** - the inability to pay debts or an unexpected challenge on someone's cash flow, might also be a problem that upsets an employee's time at work;

- **Individual's personality** - might contribute to stress. People's dispositions (how they perceive things as negative or positive) can be a factor in each person's stress.

Figure 7. Individual source of stress
Source: Adapted from Lumen Learning

There are a lot of organisational sources of stress:

- **Task or role demands** - factors related to a person's position at work, including a person's job or working conditions. A stressful role or task might be when someone is expected to accomplish more in a certain amount of time than is realistic.
- **Interpersonal demands** - stressors created by co-workers. Perhaps an employee is experiencing an ongoing conflict with a co-worker that is expected to collaborate with. Or maybe they experience poor social support in the roles they play.
- **Organisational structure** - level of differentiation within an organisation, the level of rules and policies, and decisions made. If employees do not have the chance of participating in decisions that affect them, they may feel stressed.
- **Organisational leadership** - the organisation's style of leadership. Leaders can generate an environment of anxiety, fear, tension and stress and exert unrealistic pressure and control.

- **The Organisational life stage** happens when an organisation goes through a cycle of phases (birth, growth, maturity, decline). For workers, the birth and decline of an organisation can be especially stressful, as those phases tend to be characterised by heavy workloads and uncertainties about the future. In the prison context, this organisational life stage cycle applies to major changes that are implemented (concerning policies, laws, careers changes, building structures, political restructuring). Heavy workloads also characterise these phases, and until the process of adaptation and implementation ends, they are a source of uncertainties about the future.

Figure 8. Organisational source of stress
Source: Adapted from Lumen Learning

The last source of stress is **environmental**. The economy may be in a downward spiral, creating insecurity for jobs and banks. There may be political instability or change creating stress. The stressors in our environmental surroundings can be cumulative, and when stress builds up, new factors are added to peoples' stress levels. As such, a single factor of stress might not seem important at the time, but when added to other stresses, it can lead to tremendous stress levels.

Figure 9. Environmental source of stress
Source: Adapted from Lumen Learning

Those are the sources of stress, but differences within an individual determine whether that stress will be positive or negative. Those **individual differences** include:^{4, 5}

- **Perception** - it moderates the individual's relationship to the stressor. For example, prison's fair and transparent procedures are required to deal with staff and inmates' grievances. If there is a difference in how someone should proceed, this can cause great stress.
- **Job Experience** - because stress is associated with turnover, it would stand to reason that those employees with long tenure are the most stress-resistant of the bunch. For example, effective prison management necessarily involves organising staff, their duties and routines; if these tasks are not assimilated, this can be a source of additional stress.
- **Social Support** - co-workers, especially those who are caring or considered friends, can help protect a fellow employee against the effects of stress.
- **Belief in the locus of control** - people who have a high internal locus of control (those who believe they are in control of their destiny), are not as impacted by stress as those who feel they lack control.

- **Self-efficacy** - self-efficacy is an individual's belief that he/she is able to complete a task. Research indicates that employees who have high levels of self-efficacy are more resilient to the effects of stress.
- **Hostility** - some employees carry around a high level of hostility as a part of their personalities, and they are frequently distrustful of their co-workers. These personality traits make a person more vulnerable to feeling stress.

Figure 10. Individual stress differences
Source: Adapted from Lumen Learning

If those possible stress sources sneak through the individual difference and reveal themselves as stress, they will appear in various physiological, psychological, and behavioural symptoms. Add to those psychological symptoms, like tension and anxiety, but also job dissatisfaction and boredom, and behavioural symptoms, like turnover and absenteeism, and you can see how stress can become an organisational problem.

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes and check your progress in the next page...

A large, empty rectangular box with a thin black border, intended for taking notes or checking progress.

What did I learn?

- ◆ The definition of occupational stress
- ◆ The multiple sources of occupational stress
- ◆ Prison presents several stressors that put those working in this environment at a higher risk of experiencing stress;
- ◆ The ten psychosocial risk factors related to stress reactions within correctional officers
- ◆ Several studies focused on finding the consequences of occupational stress within the correctional environment
- ◆ Depending on the circumstances, stress is not necessarily bad, and a certain level of stress can be beneficial to face environmental demands appropriately
- ◆ Stress can also be negative when it is related to constraints and demands
- ◆ The definition of the General Adaptation Syndrome (GAS), and what phases does it describe
- ◆ Signs of exhaustion
- ◆ The definition of appraisal, the two different types of appraisal and reappraisal
- ◆ The definition of coping
- ◆ Several tips may help to prevent stress

Chapter 2 - Stress at Workplace

Sub-chapter 2.1 - Work and Stress

Work-related stress is a response when people are presented with work demands and pressures that are not corresponding to their knowledge or abilities and, consequently, challenge their capacity to deal with.^{1,2}

Stress occurs in a broad range of work situations but is frequently made worse when employees feel they do not have enough support from supervisors/colleagues and also have little control over work or how they can deal with its challenges and pressures.^{1,2}

Stress may result from a person's **mismatch between his/her demands and pressures** and the **knowledge and abilities**. This can include situations where work pressures exceed their ability to cope and where the employees' knowledge and abilities are not sufficiently applied, which is a problem for them.³

Excessive and unmanageable challenges and pressures can be caused by poor design, poor management and unsatisfactory working conditions. Similarly, these factors can result in **employees not receiving adequate or sufficient support from others** or not having control over work and its demands.

The **Job-Demand-Control-Support Model**⁴ considers the balance between the **control one has over its job** (low VS high job control) and the **job demands** as a predictor of job strain. The interaction concerning **job demand and job control** allows the creation of the following four quadrants:

- **High strain jobs** - these jobs are marked by **low control** while facing **high demands** and, therefore, put employees at a higher risk level;
- **Active jobs** - these present both **high demands and high control**. Therefore, professionals are expected to display average levels of job strain;

- **Low strain jobs** - characterised by a combination of **low demands and high control**, a below-average stress level is expected as a result of this combination;
- **Passive jobs** - describes a situation when employees face **low demands and have low control** over their jobs. Considering the lack of motivation this may raise, average levels of job strain are expected.

The balance between:

- The **control one has over its job (low VS high job control)**;
- The **job demands as a predictor of job strain**

Figure 11. Job-Demand-Control-Support Model
Source: Karasek, 1979

Trying to broaden the scope of this theory, a third factor to be considered was introduced, resulting in the **Demand-Control-Support theory**, or **Iso-Strain model**, therefore considering the potential **moderator/mediator effect** that social support has on health outcomes. This reformulation believes high-strain jobs will be characterised by high demands, low control, and low social support. Therefore, increased social support is expected to decrease job strain levels while the lack of social support worsens.⁴

The **Job-Demand-Control-Support Model**⁴ is a recognised theory that describes how job characteristics impact employees' psychological well-being. The model explains how job demands can cause stress for employees, such as heavy workload, role ambiguity, and job-related strain. However, the model suggests that individuals can manage these stressors by using job skills to increase autonomy and control overwork.^{5, 6}

Gaining control over the job

Making autonomous decisions is vital to gaining control over the job. Attaining this and being able to make decisions without asking for direction might require negotiation with superiors but pays off.

Support from the supervisor

Good and helpful social interactions, for example with superiors, can buffer the impact of stress by influencing job attitude, satisfaction and commitment.

Support from colleagues

Support is critical, particularly from co-workers and others in the immediate environment. Colleagues are on equal footing and can be vital companions, particularly in teams.

Increasing psychological well-being

Higher levels of optimism and self-efficacy help manage stress better. Boosting efficacy, for example through workshops, helps employees experience the positive effects of their actions.

Figure 12. Job-Demand-Control-Support Model

Source: Adapted from Karasek & Theorell (1990), Treiber & Davis (2012), Rubino et al. (2012)

When stress is chronically present, it begins to **damage a person’s body and mental state**. Increased **risk of heart attack, stroke, and blood pressure** are just some of the physical consequences. **Anxiety** and **depression** are the characteristics of psychological symptoms of stress but can also include cognitive symptoms like **forgetfulness** and **indecisiveness**. Behaviourally, a person suffering stress might be prone to sudden verbal outbursts, hostility, drug and alcohol abuse and even violence.⁷

Figure 13. Effects of stress in the human body

When **stress is not under control**, and the individual and organisation suffers from it, the following may be observed:⁷

Physical:

Figure 14. Physical consequences from stress

Emotional:

Figure 15. Emotional consequences from stress

When individuals engage in these behaviours or are in these **emotional states**, they are more prone to:⁷

Figure 16. Behavioural/emotional tendencies when stress is not under control

When work begins to overlap with employees' personal life, this **negatively affects their productivity**. Quality work is more associated with conscientiousness and personal satisfaction than workload (for example, energetic and active individuals affect productivity positively).

When work begins to overlap with employees' personal life, this **negatively affects their productivity**

Quality work is more associated with **conscientiousness and personal satisfaction**

A randomised sample of 425 employees in the private and public sectors identified the responsible factors that influenced productivity. Many useful aspects regarding the function of stress, satisfaction and supportive elements on productivity were presented. As expected, **high stress leads to reduced productivity, and high satisfaction leads to increased productivity**.⁸

Figure 17. Responsible factors that influence productivity

There is no question that in several cases, productivity is related to aspects that are external to the individual but affect performance (for example, a salesperson's performance is related to market mobility, regardless of the persuasion he/she may possess). In many cases, **an individual's work performance is directly related to the**

performance of other employees in the same environment, so the individual cannot set his/her standards, especially if there are some informal social rules.⁸

It is believed that **job satisfaction is directly correlated with the mental health of the workforce** and the organisations' interest in high productivity and a stable and permanent workforce. On the other hand, stress is the main trigger of problems in individuals' professional and in their **private lives**. It can also produce **physical and psychosomatic symptoms**. A stress-filled employee makes **wrong decisions** and has **negative relationships** with co-workers. Both these aspects can bear a negative outcome in the productivity of a group, thus creating an added cost to a company. **Reduced productivity, mistakes, low quality work and absenteeism** are indicators of a stressed individual.¹⁰

On the other hand, **a happy employee is a crucial requirement for a healthy organisation**.⁹ **Work-related stress is an essential factor in job satisfaction**. When it functions as a **motivator**, it results in creativity and satisfaction and consequently dissolves boredom and mundaneness. When stress functions as a negative factor, it results in aggression and low job satisfaction. Job satisfaction can lead to the prevention of stressors through job incentives.¹¹

Job satisfaction is directly correlated with **the mental health of the workforce**

On the other hand, stress is the main trigger of problems in individuals' professional and in their **private lives**

Reduced productivity, mistakes, low quality work and absenteeism are indicators of a stressed individual.

Happy employee is a crucial requirement for a **healthy organisation**

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

A large, empty rectangular box with a thin black border, intended for taking notes or observations.

Sub-chapter 2.2 - The interaction between the task, the individual, and the employer

Most of the causes of work stress concern how work is designed and how organisations are managed. We can have a condition that concern the **work content** (job content, workload and work pace, working hours, participation and control) and **work context** (career development, status and play, role in the organisation, interpersonal relationships, organisational culture, and home-work interface).^{1, 2}

How **work is designed** and **organisations are managed**

Work content

Work context

Work content:

Job content

- Monotonous, under-stimulating, meaningless tasks
- Lack of variety
- Unpleasant tasks
- Aversive tasks
- Skills/abilities do not match job demands
- Lack of training and/or preparation (technical)

Workload and work pace

- Having too much or too little to do
- Working under pressures

Figure 18. Work content factors

Figure 19. Work content factors

Work context:

Figure 20. Work context factors

Organisational culture

- Poor communication
- Poor leadership
- Lack of clarity of organisational objectives and structure
- Participation (or non-participation) in decision-making
- Communication patterns (poor communication / information flow)
- Little recognition for good job performance
- Lack of systems in the workplace available to respond to concerns
- Not engaging employees when undergoing organisational change
- Lack of perceived fairness (who gets what when and the processes through which decisions are made). Feelings of unfairness magnify the effects of perceived stress on health
- Lack of support (such as family-friendly policies, employee assistance programs, etc.)

Home-work interface

- Conflicting demands of work and home
- Family exposed to work-related hazards
- Lack of support for domestic problems at work
- Lack of support for work problems at home

Figure 21. Work context factors

Setting the right level of goals, making sure the job design is balanced and that work environments are supportive and encouraging are some of the challenges leaders face daily to control stress in the workplace. They can also provide the employee with healthy

choices to manage his/her stress levels via programs and benefits that encourage self-care.^{3, 4}

Figure 22. Relationship between arousal and performance
Source: Adapted from *The Yerkes-Dodson Law and Performance*

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

A large, empty rectangular box with a thin black border, intended for taking notes or observations.

Sub-chapter 2.3 - Work and Burnout

According to the International Classification of Diseases:¹

“Burnout is a syndrome conceptualised as resulting from chronic workplace stress that has not been successfully managed. It is characterised by three dimensions: 1) feelings of energy depletion or exhaustion; 2) increased mental distance from one’s job, or feelings of negativism or cynicism related to one’s job; and 3) a sense of ineffectiveness and lack of accomplishment. Burn-out refers specifically to phenomena in the occupational context and should not be applied to describe experiences in other areas of life.”

This definition adopts these three components: (1) **exhaustion**, the depletion of one’s mental resources at work; (2) **cynicism**, a distant attitude toward the job; and (3) **reduced professional efficacy**, a lack of achievement and productivity at work.

Figure 23. Relationship between Productivity and Energy
Source: Adapted from James Kennedy Monash

Some authors consider that burnout comprises **four core dimensions** (exhaustion, mental distance, emotional impairment, and cognitive impairment) and **three secondary symptoms** (depressed mood, psychological distress, and psychosomatic complaints).²

Four core dimensions:

exhaustion, mental distance,
emotional impairment, and cognitive
impairment

Three secondary symptoms:

depressed mood, psychological
distress, and psychosomatic
complaints

What Causes Job Burnout?³

The causes for burnout are:

Figure 24. Causes for burnout

What are the Signs of Burnout?³

There are several **indicators and symptoms related to burnout**. The main point is that the symptoms of burnout are usually thought to be triggered by work-related stress. Here is what to look for:

Physical Warning Signs and Symptoms

Figure 25. Physical warning signs and symptoms of burnout

Emotional Warning Signs and Symptoms

01

Sense of failure and self-doubt

02

Feeling helpless, trapped, and defeated

03

Detachment, feeling alone

04

Loss of motivation

05

A cynical and negative outlook

06

Decreased satisfaction and sense of accomplishment

Behavioural Warning Signs and Symptoms

01

Withdrawing from responsibilities

02

Isolating yourself

03

Procrastinating

04

Using food, drugs, or alcohol to cope

05

Taking out frustrations on others

06

Skipping work, being late, leaving early

The 12 Stages of Burnout are:⁴

Figure 26. The 12 stages of burnout

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes and check your progress in the next page...

A large, empty rectangular box with a thin black border, intended for taking notes or checking progress.

What did I learn?

- ◆ The Definition of Job-Demand-Control-Support Model
- ◆ The Definition of Demand-Control-Support theory/Iso-Strain model
- ◆ The physical and emotional effects of stress
- ◆ The effects of stress on work productivity
- ◆ The relation between work-related stress and job satisfaction
- ◆ Definition of burnout
- ◆ What causes job burnout
- ◆ What are the (physical, emotional and behavioural) signs of burnout
- ◆ The 12 Stages of Burnout

Chapter 3 - Stress and Leadership

Sub-chapter 3.1 - The importance of Leadership in stress management at the workplace

Leaders' behaviour and leadership have been considered important job resources.¹ Good leaders can increase employees' well-being by improving the working environment, the organisation of work, and the social context, considering employees' unique characteristics.² However, the same employees with formal leadership roles can have a negative impact on organisations, increasing employees' stress by excessive workload and role ambiguity, as well as discretionary practices in terms of performance assessment, recognition and rewards.

Autocratic Leadership behaviours are expected to be outdated and not consonant with employees' needs and expectations in challenging work environments. Thus, **Transformational Leadership**, characterised by "idealised influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualised consideration",³ (p. 112) was conceptualised and studied since it appears to generate new/or improve existing resources that leverage followers' well-being.

There are **four health promotion leadership levels: environmental, social, organisational, and individual**. It is debated that health promotion interventions should not be restricted to one level. Instead, an integrated approach should be adopted. The relation between the four levels and the results should be analysed. It is indicated that these four levels are used as a checklist when health promotion interventions are planned.⁴

The **management model** holds **four levels** and several steps that can help establish a health-promoting leadership. The **first** is described as a goal - and task-oriented management, in which leadership is defined as a goal-oriented effort of influence.⁵ For example, set/agree on goals for the staff, control implementation and give feedback. The **second** includes staff-oriented support and management. For example, involve and participate, show appreciation, be a role model, train and further develop staff, show

social and organisation support, consider the personal situation of the staff, activate and encourage the staff. The **third** concerns the work and organisational procedures (which is another crucial sign of a good leadership culture). For example, create or improve physical working conditions (too hot or too cold, provide equipment or tools), make work procedures transparent and clear, organise collaboration between the staff, and ensure unhindered information flow. Finally, the **fourth** level suggests the creation of health-promoting management and organisational culture. For example, by creating a cooperative action, admitting errors, and learning from them, creating health consciousness, creating an atmosphere of trust, and finally having a vision and developing health-promoting actions.⁶

Figure 27. Heuristic Model of Organizational Health
Source: Adapted from Hart and Cooper, 2001

What did I learn?

- ◆ Good leaders can increase employees' well-being
- ◆ The four levels of health promotion leadership
- ◆ What is the management model

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes and check your progress in the next page...

References

Chapter 1 - Understanding Stress

Sub-chapter 1.1 - The importance of well-being and mental health in workplace settings

- ¹ Fraser, A. (2014). Staff health and well-being in prisons: leadership and training. In S. Enggist, L. Mølle, G. Galea, & C. Udesen (Eds.), *Prisons and health* (pp. 185–189). World Health Organization.
- ² Harms, P. D., Credé, M., Tynan, M., Leon, M., & Jeung, W. (2017). Leadership and stress: A meta-analytic review. *Leadership Quarterly*, 28(1), 178–194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2016.10.006>
- ³ Ardid, C., & Zarco, V. (2001). El estrés laboral. In A. R. Fernández (Ed.), *Introducción a la Psicología del Trabajo y de las Organizaciones* (pp. 235–246). Pirámide.
- ⁴ Camara, P. B., Guerra, P. B., & Rodrigues, J. V. (2013). *Humanator XXI* (6th ed.). D. Quixote.
- ⁵ Guez, F., & Delhommeau, A.-C. (2009). *Agir sur le stress au travail*. Nathan.
- ⁶ Schaufeli, W. B., & Peeters, M. (2000). Job stress and burnout among correctional officers: A literature review. *International Journal of Stress Management*, 7(1), 19–48. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1009514731657>
- ⁷ Dowden, C., & Tellier, C. (2004). Predicting work-related stress in correctional officers: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 32(1), 31–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcrimjus.2003.10.003>
- ⁸ Finney, C., Stergiopoulos, E., Hensel, J., Bonato, S., & Dewa, C. S. (2013). Organisational stressors associated with job stress and burnout in correctional officers: a systematic review. *BMC Public Health*, 13, 82. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-13-82>
- ⁹ Bezerra, C. de M., de Assis, S. G., & Constantino, P. (2016). Sofrimento psíquico e estresse no trabalho de agentes penitenciários: Uma revisão da literatura. *Ciência e Saúde Coletiva*, 21(7), 2135–2146. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1413-81232015217.00502016>
- ¹⁰ Butler, H. D. D., Tasca, M., Zhang, Y., & Carpenter, C. (2019). A systematic and meta-analytic review of the literature on correctional officers: Identifying new avenues for research. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 60(January–February), 84–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcrimjus.2018.12.002>
- ¹¹ Schiff, M., & Leip, L. (2019). The Impact of Job Expectations, Workload, and Autonomy on Work-Related Stress Among Prison Wardens in the United States. *Criminal Justice and Behavior*, 46(1), 136–153. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0093854818802876>
- ¹² Steiner, B., & Wooldredge, J. (2015). Individual and Environmental Sources of Work Stress Among Prison Officers. *Criminal Justice and Behavior*, 42(8), 800–818. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0093854814564463>
- ¹³ Akbari, J., Akbari, R., Shakerian, M., & Mahaki, B. (2017). Job demand-control and job stress at work: A cross-sectional study among prison staff. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*, 6, 15. https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp_68_14
- ¹⁴ Shepherd, B. R., Fritz, C., Hammer, L. B., Guros, F., & Meier, D. (2019). Emotional demands and alcohol use in corrections: A moderated mediation model. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 24(4), 438–449. <https://doi.org/10.1037/ocp0000114>
- ¹⁵ Useche, S. A., Montoro, L. V., Ruiz, J. I., Vanegas, C., Sanmartin, J., & Alfaro, E. (2019). Workplace burnout and health issues among Colombian correctional officers. *Plos One*, 14(2), e0211447. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0211447>

- ¹⁶ Cho, S., Noh, H., Yang, E., Lee, J., Lee, N., Schaufeli, W. B., & Lee, S. M. (2020). Examining the job demands-resources model in a sample of Korean correctional officers. *Current Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-020-00620-8>
- ¹⁷ Kinman, G., Clements, A. J., & Hart, J. (2017a). Job demands, resources and mental health in U.K. prison officers. *Occupational Medicine*, 67(6), 456–460. <https://doi.org/10.1093/OCCMED/KQX091>
- ¹⁸ Lambert, E. G., Keena, L. D., Haynes, S. H., May, D., & Leone, M. (2020). Predictors of Job Stress Among Southern Correctional Staff. *Criminal Justice Policy Review*, 31(2), 309–331. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0887403419829211>
- ¹⁹ Lambert, E. G., Worley, R., & Worley, V. B. (2018). The effects of perceptions of staff-inmate boundary violations and willingness to follow rules upon work stress. *Security Journal*, 31(2), 618–644. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41284-017-0121-2>
- ²⁰ Otu, S., Lambert, E. G., & Elechi, O. O. (2018). Testing the job demands-resources model for Nigerian prison staff job stress. *Howard Journal of Crime and Justice*, 57(2), 152–181. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hojo.12245>
- ²¹ Paoline, E. A., Lambert, E. G. E. G., & Hogan, N. L. N. L. (2015). Job Stress and Job Satisfaction Among Jail Staff: Exploring Gendered Effects. *Women & Criminal Justice*, 25(5), 339–359. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08974454.2014.989302>
- ²² Jin, X., Sun, I. Y., Jiang, S., Wang, Y., & Wen, S. (2018a). The impact of job characteristics on burnout among Chinese correctional workers. *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology*, 62(2), 551–570. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306624X16648419>
- ²³ Jin, X., Sun, I. Y., Jiang, S., Wang, Y., & Wen, S. (2018b). The relationships between job and organisational characteristics and role and job stress among Chinese community correctional workers. *International Journal of Law, Crime and Justice*, 52, 36–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijlcrj.2017.09.002>
- ²⁴ Mack, K. Y., & Rhineberger-Dunn, G. (2019). The influence of work–family conflict on job stress among two groups of community corrections staff. *Journal of Crime and Justice*, 42(3), 350–363. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0735648X.2018.1528879>
- ²⁵ Lambert, E. G., Kim, B., Keena, L. D., & Cheeseman, K. (2017). Testing a gendered models of job satisfaction and work stress among correctional officers. *Journal of Crime and Justice*, 40(2), 188–203. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0735648X.2015.1074092>
- ²⁶ Armstrong, G. S., Atkin-Plunk, C. A., & Wells, J. (2015). The Relationship Between Work–Family Conflict, Correctional Officer Job Stress, and Job Satisfaction. *Criminal Justice and Behavior*, 42(10), 1066–1082. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0093854815582221>
- ²⁷ Farnese, M. L., Barbieri, B., Bello, B., & Bartone, P. T. (2017). Don't abandon hope all ye who enter here: The protective role of formal mentoring and learning processes on burnout in correctional officers. *Work-a Journal of Prevention Assessment & Rehabilitation*, 58(3), 319–331. <https://doi.org/10.3233/wor-172628>
- ²⁸ Schaufeli, W. B., & Taris, T. W. (2014). A Critical Review of the Job Demands-Resources Model: Implications for Improving Work and Health. In G. F. Bauer & O. Hämmig (Eds.), *Bridging Occupational, Organizational and Public Health: A Transdisciplinary Approach* (pp. 43–68). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-5640-3>

Sub-chapter 1.2 - What is stress?

- ¹ Harms, P. D., Credé, M., Tynan, M., Leon, M., & Jeung, W. (2017). Leadership and stress: A meta-analytic review. *Leadership Quarterly*, 28(1), 178–194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2016.10.006>
- ² Kemeny, M. E. (2003). The Psychobiology of Stress. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 12(4), 124–129. doi:10.1111/1467-8721.01246
- ³ Ardid, C., & Zarco, V. (2001). El estrés laboral. In A. R. Fernández (Ed.), *Introducción a la Psicología del Trabajo y de las Organizaciones* (pp. 235–246). Pirámide.
- ⁴ Leshem, Y. Y., & Kuiper, P. J. C. (1996). Is there a GAS (general adaptation syndrome) response to various types of environmental stress? *Biologia Plantarum. Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02879625>
- ⁵ Biggs, A., Brough, P., & Drummond, S. (2017). Lazarus and Folkman's Psychological Stress and Coping Theory. In *The Handbook of Stress and Health* (pp. 349–364). John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118993811.ch21>
- ⁶ Leka, S., Griffiths, A., & Cox, T. (2003). World Health Organization. Occupational and Environmental Health Team. Work organisation and stress: systematic problem approaches for employers, managers and trade union representatives. Retrieved from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/42625>

Sub-chapter 1.3 - Transactional Model of Stress

- ¹ Biggs, A., Brough, P., & Drummond, S. (2017). Lazarus and Folkman's Psychological Stress and Coping Theory. In *The Handbook of Stress and Health* (pp. 349–364). John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118993811.ch21>
- ² Goh, Y. W., Sawang, S., & Oei, T. P. S. (2010). The Revised Transactional Model (RTM) of Occupational Stress and Coping: An Improved Process Approach. *The Australian and New Zealand Journal of Organisational Psychology*, 3(2010), 13–20. <https://doi.org/10.1375/ajop.3.1.13>
- ³ Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (1984). *Stress, appraisal and coping*. New York: Springer

Sub-chapter 1.4 - Levels of Stressors

- ¹ Ardid, C., & Zarco, V. (2001). El estrés laboral. In A. R. Fernández (Ed.), *Introducción a la Psicología del Trabajo y de las Organizaciones* (pp. 235–246). Pirámide.
- ² Camara, P. B., Guerra, P. B., & Rodrigues, J. V. (2013). *Humanator XXI* (6th ed.). D. Quixote.
- ³ Guez, F., & Delhommeau, A.-C. (2009). *Agir sur le stress au travail*. Nathan.
- ⁴ Makara-Studzińska, M., Wajda, Z., & Lizińczyk, S. (2020). Years of service, self-efficacy, stress and burnout among Polish firefighters. *International Journal of Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health*, 33(3), 283–297. <https://doi.org/10.13075/IJOMEH.1896.01483>
- ⁵ Ebner, K., & Singewald, N. (2017, April 1). Individual differences in stress susceptibility and stress inhibitory mechanisms. *Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences*. Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cobeha.2016.11.016>

Chapter 2 - Stress at Workplace

Sub-chapter 2.1 - Work and Stress

- ¹ Leka, S., Griffiths, A., & Cox, T. (2003). World Health Organization. Occupational and Environmental Health Team. Work organisation and stress: systematic problem approaches for employers, managers and trade union representatives. Retrieved from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/42625>
- ² Lambert, E.G., Hogan, N. L., Keena, L. D., Williamson, L. & Kim, B. (2017). Exploring the Association between Different Types of Social Support with Role Stress, Work–family Conflict, and Turnover Intent among Private Prison Staff. *Journal of Applied Security Research*, 12:2, 203–223. doi:10.1080/19361610.2017.1277866
- ³ Ardid, C., & Zarco, V. (2001). El estrés laboral. In A. R. Fernández (Ed.), *Introducción a la Psicología del Trabajo y de las Organizaciones* (pp. 235–246). Pirámide.
- ⁴ Cox, T., & Griffiths, A. (2010). Work-related stress: a theoretical perspective. In S. Leka & J. Houndmont (Eds.), *Occupational Health Psychology* (pp. 31–56). Wiley Blackwell.
- ⁵ Rubino, C., Perry, S. J., Milam, A. C., Spitzmueller, C., & Zapf, D. (2012). Demand–control–person: Integrating the demand–control and conservation of resources models to test an expanded stressor–strain model. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 17(4), 456–472. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0029718>
- ⁶ Treiber, L. A., & Davis, S. N. (2012). The role of ‘workplace family’ support on worker health, exhaustion and pain. *Community, Work & Family*, 15(1), 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13668803.2011.580123>

- ⁷ Kemeny, M. E. (2003). The Psychobiology of Stress. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 12(4), 124–129. doi:10.1111/1467-8721.01246
- ⁸ Havermans, B. M., Brouwers, E. P. M., Hoek, R. J. A., Anema, J. R., Van Der Beek, A. J., & Boot, C. R. L. (2018). Work stress prevention needs of employees and supervisors. *BMC Public Health*, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-018-5535-1>
- ⁹ Hellebuyck, M., Nguyen, T., Halphern, M., Fritze, D., & Kennedy, J. (2017). Mind the Workplace: Workplace Mental Health 2017. Retrieved from: <http://hdl.handle.net/10713/14084>
- ¹⁰ Lakshmi Narahari, C., & Koneru, K. (2018). Stress at work place and its impact on employee performance. *International Journal of Engineering and Technology* (UAE), 7(2), 1066–1071. <https://doi.org/10.14419/ijet.v7i2.7.12229>
- ¹¹ Lambert, E., Hogan, N., Keena, L., Williamson, L., & Kim, B. (2017). Exploring the Association between Different Types of Social Support with Role Stress, Work–family Conflict, and Turnover Intent among Private Prison Staff. *Journal of Applied Security Research*, 12:2, 203-223. doi:10.1080/19361610.2017.1277866

Sub-chapter 2.2 - The interaction between the task, the individual, and the employer

- ¹ Halkos, G. & Bousinakis, D. (2010). The effect of stress and satisfaction on productivity. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 59(5), pp. 415-431. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17410401011052869>
- ² Havermans, B. M., Brouwers, E. P. M., Hoek, R. J. A., Anema, J. R., Van Der Beek, A. J., & Boot, C. R. L. (2018). Work stress prevention needs of employees and supervisors. *BMC Public Health*, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-018-5535-1>
- ³ Lakshmi Narahari, C., & Koneru, K. (2018). Stress at work place and its impact on employee performance. *International Journal of Engineering and Technology* (UAE), 7(2), 1066–1071. <https://doi.org/10.14419/ijet.v7i2.7.12229>
- ⁴ Leka, S., Griffiths, A., & Cox, T. (2003). World Health Organization. Occupational and Environmental Health Team. Work organisation and stress: systematic problem approaches for employers, managers and trade union representatives. Retrieved from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/42625>

Sub-chapter 2.3 - Work and Burnout

- ¹ World Health Organization. (2020). *QD85 Burnout*. ICD-11. [Open Access] Retrieved from: <http://id.who.int/icd/entity/129180281>
- ² Schaufeli, W. B., Desart, S., & De Witte, H. (2020). Burnout assessment tool (Bat)—development, validity, and reliability. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(24), 1–21. doi:10.3390/ijerph17249495
- ³ Formscore. *Work*, 2021. [Open Access] Retrieved from: <https://www.formscore.today/articles/are-we-facing-a-crisis-of-burnout>
- ⁴ Florence Jimenez Otto. *12 stages of burnout according to psychologists Herbert Freudenberger and Gail North*. [Open Access] Retrieved from: <https://florencejimenezotto.com/2019/01/14/12-stages-of-burnout-according-to-psychologists-herbert-freudenberger-and-gail-north/>

Chapter 3 - Stress and Leadership

Sub-chapter 3.1 - The importance of Leadership in stress management at the workplace

- ¹ Schaufeli, W. B., & Taris, T. W. (2014). A Critical Review of the Job Demands-Resources Model: Implications for Improving Work and Health. In G. F. Bauer & O. Hämmig (Eds.), *Bridging Occupational, Organizational and Public Health: A Transdisciplinary Approach* (pp. 43–68). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-5640-3>
- ² Peiró, J., & Rodríguez, I. (2008). Estrés laboral, liderazgo y salud organizacional. *Papeles Del Psicólogo*, 29(1), 68–82. <http://www.cop.es/papeles>
- ³ Bass, B. M., & Avolio, B. J. (1993). Transformational Leadership and Organizational Culture. *Public Administration Quarterly*, 112–121. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40862298>
- ⁴ Kelly, M.P., Charlton, B.G., & Hanlon, P. (1993). The four levels of health promotion: an integrated approach. *Public Health*, 107(5):319-26. doi:10.1016/s0033-3506(05)80123-4
- ⁵ Spiess, E., & Stadler, P. (2016). Four-level model of health-promoting leadership. In *Healthy at Work* (pp. 103-113). Springer, Cham.
- ⁶ Yao, L., Li, P., & Wildy, H. (2021). Health-Promoting Leadership: Concept, Measurement, and Research Framework. *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.602333>

LEADCOR

LEADERSHIP DEVELOPMENT FOR OCCUPATIONAL
STRESS REDUCTION IN CORRECTIONAL SETTINGS

